

THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN EDUCATION FOR THE SUSTAINABLE FUTURE OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract

The Role of women in education, political participation and in a society plays a larger role in the development of the society, state and the country, because without women's progress in education and political participation, the development of a state and the society is a dream task for any state, most of the political developed nations give equal rights and status for women literacy, education and overall progress of the state. Serious efforts must be made by the government in collaboration with civil society wherein awareness must be created amongst the parents for promoting girls education. Use of media in the portraying a positive image of women, financial assistance to the poverty stricken families. Counselling of parents and children from unprivileged families. India is the largest country in terms of population, but India still far behind for achieving the sustainable future in women's education. In India Still there is highest percentage of male literates compare to female literacy, due to cultural differences and political participation of more male politician's compared to female politicians. The research paper is to enrich the role of women's education for the sustainable future in development of political development of the state and constraints for the development of the country.

Key words: *Women Education, political participation of women in the state, Sustainable Future.*

Introduction

Political Participation of women involves the participation of women in the elections as a representative from village panchayats to the prime posts in the Country, states for the sustainable political future of the Country, and it can be possible from the education of the women in the states from the primary education level to the political representation levels, The principle of gender equality is enshrined in the Indian Constitution in its Preamble, Fundamental Rights, Fundamental Duties and Directive Principles. The Constitution not only grants equality to women, but also empowers the State to adopt measures of positive discrimination in favour of women. Within the framework of the democratic polity, our laws,

development policies, Plans and programmes have aimed at women's advancement in different spheres. India has also ratified various international conventions and human rights instruments committing to secure equal rights of women. Key among them is the ratification of the Convention on Elimination of All forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) in 1993.

Political participation of Women and its role

Education as means of empowerment of women can bring about a positive attitudinal change. It is therefore, crucial for the socio- economic and political progress of India. The Constitution of India empowers the state to adopt affirmative measures for prompting ways and means to empower women. As per a UN report, education for women is the single most effective way to improve lives and health of a family and a society and political participation at large. A woman with education is a powerful person, she has the power to educate the children in her family, guide them in taking decisions, contribute economically and offer valuable inputs for improvement on home and social front. Women constitute almost half of a country's population, when 50% of the population is denied education – a nation remains underdeveloped. Empowered women contribute to the development of the society; Education is the most important power that shapes the lives of mankind. It empowers with the ability to think, reason, take appropriate decisions and protect oneself from oppression & abuse. However, in most of the developing world around the globe including India, women are often denied of education opportunities. Even though, women constitute 48% of the total

population in India – the women literacy rate in urban area is 79.11% as against 88.76% males, and the figures are even lower in the rural scenario where 57.93% women are literate as against 77.15% literate males. In 2014,

Special Provisions for women in India

➤ **National Commission for Women**

In January 1992, the Government set-up this statutory body with a specific mandate to study and monitor all matters relating to the constitutional and legal safeguards provided for women, review the existing legislation to suggest amendments wherever necessary, etc.

➤ **Reservation for Women in Local Self -Government**

The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Acts passed in 1992 by Parliament ensure one-third of the total seats for women in all elected offices in local bodies whether in rural areas or urban areas.

➤ **The National Plan of Action for the Girl Child (1991-2000)**

The plan of Action is to ensure survival, protection and development of the girl child with the ultimate objective of building up a better future for the girl child.

National Policy for the Empowerment of Women, 2001

The Department of Women & Child Development in the Ministry of Human Resource Development has prepared a “**National Policy for the Empowerment of Women**” in the year 2001. The goal of this policy is to bring about the advancement, development and empowerment of women.

Review of Literature

United Nations Declaration on Human Rights Education and Training

The General Assembly

Reaffirming the purposes and principles of the Charter of the United Nations with regard to the promotion and encouragement of respect for all human rights and fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language or religion, and also that every individual and every organ of society shall strive by teaching and education to promote respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms,

Benefits of Women education

- There are numerous benefits of women education. Here are few of them:
 - Women who are educated are able to take charge of their future
 - They earn and contribute to their family income
 - Women who are educated help reduce child and maternal mortality
 - Educated women are better equipped to take care of their children
 - They are less likely to be taken advantage of and lowers exposure to domestic abuse

- Have great confidence and takes right decisions
- Contributes in a positive way to the society and the nation at large
- When women are included in key decision-making positions, they take holistic decisions for the development of the society
- Including women in politics tend to have different growth dimensions

Scope

Article 14 (d) sets out the right to education of rural women, which includes the right to obtain all types of training and education, formal and non-formal, including that relating to functional literacy. Lastly Article 16 sets out the rights of women with respects to marriage and family life. The Constitution of India, under Articles 14, 15 and 16, is deeply committed to the right to equality as a fundamental right. The Articles guarantee equality before the law and equal protection of the laws (Article 14), prohibition of discrimination on the grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth (Article 15), and equality of opportunity in matters of public employment (Article 16). However, the right to equality under the Constitution also allows the State to make positive discrimination in favour of certain classes of citizens such as women, children, socially and educationally backward classes, scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. The founding father of the Indian Constitution, Dr B.R. Ambedkar was of the view that in order to be lasting, social reform must precede political reform and that without according political power to the Depressed Classes their status would not improve.

Conclusion

For women is very important for the improvement of women's education country especially in political participation and social welfare of the country without women's education the countries future political participation cannot be performed. The woman plays a larger role in the development and for a sustainable future of the country because due to the education of women the literacy rate can be improved all the also the political participation of women can also develop the sustainable political development in a state or the country.

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